

Compound Events in Ethiopia

 IVM Institute for
Environmental Studies

Welcome to the survey!

With this survey we want to understand how simultaneous and/or consecutive natural and socio-economic events in *Ethiopia* combine together, reducing or increasing the risk of national crises.

Through the following questions, we will gain insights on the impacts and related drivers that have marked the humanitarian crises experienced in Ethiopia in the years: *2017-2018* and *2019-2020*. The results of this survey are essential to support researchers and national agencies in developing robust multi-hazard risk assessments.

We thank you for taking the time to provide us with your unique knowledge and experience. In this survey, there are no correct or incorrect answers, and no answers are better or worse than other. We are interested in your personal point of you and experience.

Your answers in this study will remain confidential and anonymised. We will minimize any risks by storing the collected research data on VU servers, which can only be accessed by the project team according to [VU confidentiality and data handling](#).

If you want to be informed about the results of this survey, enter your email here:

Part 1: Respondent Information

Initials:

optional

What is your age?

- 18 - 24 years old
 25 - 34 years old
 35 - 44 years old
 45 - 60 years old
 above 60 years old

Organization:

Department:

Position/Role:

Please indicate the highest degree/qualification you have completed *

- College/pre-university (e.g., high school)
 Undergraduate (e.g., BA, BSc)
 Master (e.g., MsC, MA)
 Doctor (e.g., MPhil, PhD)
 Other (specify manually)

Please specify your qualification.

Which areas best describe your professional background or expertise? *

Please select a maximum of two options.

- Technology, Engineering
 Management, Administration
 Infrastructure design, Architecture
 Policy, Regulation, Governance
 Science, Research
 Organization support, Logistics
 Economics, Finance

What is your main task/responsibility in your organization?

Do you work mostly at... ? *

- Regional level
 National level
 County level
 Local level (e.g. field offices)

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Part 2: Events between January 2017 - June 2018

In 2017-2018, a series of consecutive/simultaneous events occurred in Ethiopia, leading to a humanitarian crisis that saw 8 million people under food insecurity and around 1.7 millions displaced from their homes.

Here the link to a short video recalling some of the events that occurred in Ethiopia in 2017-2018: [Video](#).

2.1 Apart from the events mentioned in the above videos, what other relevant natural and socio-economic events do you recall in Ethiopia between 2017 and 2018?

List as many as you can, separated by commas.

e.g., dry spells, dam failure, ethnic clashes, economic inflation, demographic change

Below, a preliminary *Events Timeline* with some of the events that could have potentially influenced the humanitarian crisis experienced in 2017-2018. *

2.2 Are there any relevant events not mentioned?

- Some relevant events are missing.
- The Events Timeline is complete.

2.2.1 Which relevant events are missing from the above Events Timeline and when do they occur? *

List events with the approximate date in brackets and separated by commas.

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Several impacts, usually experienced during different types of disasters, are listed in the sub-categories below.

2.3 Which among them do you recall in the analysed period?

a. Impacts occurred from Jan.-Dec. 2017

Please select all the impacts that you remember occurred in Ethiopia in 2017 from each sub-category

Socio-economic impacts

- Deterioration of health conditions Food insecurity Increase of staple food prices
 Shortage of water supplies Worsening of water quality Death and injuries
 Damage to livestock Damage to crops
 Decrease of hydro-electric power production Business interruption/underperforming
 Worsening in economic conditions (slow in GDP growth) Decrease in tourism
 Population displacement Increase of social conflict Other

Damage to infrastructure

- Damage to cultural or heritage sites Damage to homes and buildings
 Damage to communications (bridges, roads, etc..) Damage to irrigation infrastructure
 Damage to flood protection infrastructure Other

Triggered disasters

- Siltation of land Subsidence Landslides/Mudslides
 Dams spillages/failures Forest/bush fires Other

Damage to the natural system

- Overexploitation of aquifers Environmental pollution Ecological damage
 Other

What *other* impacts occurred in 2017?

Provide a brief description of other impacts that occurred in 2017 not mentioned in the above list.

b. Impacts occurred from Jan.-Jun. 2018

Please select all the impacts that you remember occurred in Ethiopia in 2018 from each sub-category

Socio-economic impacts

- Deterioration of health conditions Food insecurity Increase of staple food prices
 Shortage of water supplies Worsening of water quality Death and injuries
 Damage to livestock Damage to crops
 Decrease of hydro-electric power production Business interruption/underperforming
 Worsening in economic conditions (slow in GDP growth) Decrease in tourism
 Population displacement Increase of social conflict Other

Damage to infrastructure

- Damage to cultural or heritage sites Damage to homes and buildings
 Damage to communications (bridges, roads, etc..) Damage to irrigation infrastructure
 Damage to flood protection infrastructure Other

Triggered disasters

- Siltation of land
- Subsidence
- Landslides/Mudslides
- Dams spillages/failures
- Forest/bush fires
- Other

Damage of the natural system

- Overexploitation of aquifers
- Environmental pollution
- Ecological damage
- Other

What *other* impacts occurred in 2018?

Provide a brief description of other impacts that occurred in 2017 not mentioned in the above list.

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2.4 Among the impacts selected in question 2.3, identify 4 *major* impacts, that you think led to the experienced humanitarian crisis. Classify them from 1 (the highest) to 4 (the lowest) based on their relevance/magnitude.

Major impacts according to their magnitude and related needed resources to provide adequate response.

1st Impact

*

2nd Impact

*

3rd Impact

4th Impact

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» 2b. The Root Causes of the impacts between January 2017 - June 2018

2.5 At first glance, what do you think were the natural and societal drivers, the combination of which resulted in the aforementioned impacts?

List potential drivers, separated by commas. The term drivers refers to the events/factors that caused or mitigated the previously identified impacts.

Write down the first drivers that come to your mind.

Listed below are some potential drivers of the impacts you selected in the previous questions. *

2.6 Which of these drivers do you think played a major role in mitigating or amplifying the impacts occurred in 2017 and 2018?

Try to identify a minimum of 4 major drivers

- | | | |
|--|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Flood | <input type="checkbox"/> Drought | <input type="checkbox"/> Landslides |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Dams spillage/failures | <input type="checkbox"/> Wildfire | <input type="checkbox"/> Crop pests |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Disease outbreak | <input type="checkbox"/> Refugee influx | <input type="checkbox"/> Water Management |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Conflicts/Violence/Protests | <input type="checkbox"/> Speculators/Economic Interests | <input type="checkbox"/> Land use management |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Government elections | <input type="checkbox"/> External donor funds | <input type="checkbox"/> Warning Information |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Government/County response | <input type="checkbox"/> Political disruption | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |

2.6.1 What other drivers do you consider relevant?

Provide a brief description of other drivers that mitigated or amplified the impacts experienced.

Selected drivers: - - - - -

2.7 Among the drivers selected in question 2.6, identify 4 major drives in terms of their effect on the identified impacts.

Please, motivate your answer by providing a short description (max. 10 words) on how do you think these drivers mitigated/exacerbated the analysed humanitarian crisis. In the last column of the table, assign a grade from 0 (lowest) to 5 (highest) to the selected driver according to their influence on the impacts.

Drivers	Motivation	Rating
Select Driver	* Please try to use max 10 - 15 words (e.g., using bullet points)	
Select Driver	* Please try to use max 10 - 15 words (e.g., using bullet points)	
Select Driver	Enter some text	
Select Driver	Please try to use max 10 - 15 words (e.g., using bullet points)	

» 2c. Interaction between Impacts and Drivers

2.8 Did the listed drivers reduce or amplify the impacts?

Please, fill in the below table. If the driver contributed to amplify the impact use: + (slightly amplified) or ++ (largely amplified), on the contrary use - (slightly reduced) or -- (largely reduced). If the event had no effect on that impact, select 0.

Drivers/Impacts				
	<input type="radio"/> -- <input type="radio"/> - <input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> + <input type="radio"/> ++	<input type="radio"/> -- <input type="radio"/> - <input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> + <input type="radio"/> ++	<input type="radio"/> -- <input type="radio"/> - <input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> + <input type="radio"/> ++	<input type="radio"/> -- <input type="radio"/> - <input type="radio"/> 0 <input type="radio"/> + <input type="radio"/> ++
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» 2d. Response Actions between January 2017 - June 2018

2.9 In terms of flood and drought events only, we ask you to provide your view of the response actions taken by the following Actors to mitigate related impacts.

Actors	What actions have been taken to mitigate drought impacts by the following actors?	What actions have been taken to mitigate flood impacts by the following actors?	When were these actions taken with respect to the event timeframe?	Did the drought response actions influence the subsequent flood impacts?
Government Institutions	<i>For each action, specify the responsible government institution in brackets</i>	<i>For each action, specify the responsible government institution in brackets</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Before drought <input type="checkbox"/> During drought <input type="checkbox"/> After drought <input type="checkbox"/> Before flood <input type="checkbox"/> During flood <input type="checkbox"/> After flood	<input type="radio"/> Yes, by amplifying the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> Yes, by reducing the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> No
Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions amplified the flood impacts?		Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions reduced the flood impacts?		
International Community			<input type="checkbox"/> Before drought <input type="checkbox"/> During drought <input type="checkbox"/> After drought <input type="checkbox"/> Before flood <input type="checkbox"/> During flood <input type="checkbox"/> After flood	<input type="radio"/> Yes, by amplifying the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> Yes, by reducing the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> No
Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions amplified the flood impacts?		Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions reduced the flood impacts?		

<p>NGOs</p>			<input type="checkbox"/> Before drought <input type="checkbox"/> During drought <input type="checkbox"/> After drought <input type="checkbox"/> Before flood <input type="checkbox"/> During flood <input type="checkbox"/> After flood	<input type="radio"/> Yes, by amplifying the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> Yes, by reducing the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> No
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<p>Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions amplified the flood impacts?</p>	<p>Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions reduced the flood impacts?</p>
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<p>Local Communities</p>			<input type="checkbox"/> Before drought <input type="checkbox"/> During drought <input type="checkbox"/> After drought <input type="checkbox"/> Before flood <input type="checkbox"/> During flood <input type="checkbox"/> After flood	<input type="radio"/> Yes, by amplifying the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> Yes, by reducing the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> No
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<p>Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions amplified the flood impacts?</p>	<p>Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions reduced the flood impacts?</p>
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<p>Private Sectors</p>			<input type="checkbox"/> Before drought <input type="checkbox"/> During drought <input type="checkbox"/> After drought <input type="checkbox"/> Before flood <input type="checkbox"/> During flood <input type="checkbox"/> After flood	<input type="radio"/> Yes, by amplifying the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> Yes, by reducing the flood impacts <input type="radio"/> No
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<p>Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions amplified the flood impacts?</p>	<p>Could you give a few examples of how drought response actions reduced the flood impacts?</p>
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2.10 If the aforementioned actors had been aware of the subsequent flood event months earlier, how should their actions in response to the previous drought have been different? (i.e. to avoid amplifying impacts of the subsequent flood)

Try to limit your answer up to 15 - 20 words (e.g., using bullet points)

Aforementioned actors: Government Institutions, International Community, NGOs, Local Communities.

2.11 What kind of information could have been relevant to reduce the impact? Who should have received this information and when?

Try to limit your answer up to 15 - 20 words (e.g., using bullet points)

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Part 3: Compound Events in late 2019 and 2020

Ethiopia has experienced unprecedented events in late 2019 and 2020, leading to complex physical and societal mechanisms and ultimately amplifying the impact of single extremes.

Here is a link to a short video that recall some of the events that occurred in Ethiopia in 2020:

[Video.](#)

3.1 What made the 2020 events worse or better than 2017-2018?

Please try to use max 15 words

3.2 Were there any underlying conditions present prior to the events mentioned above that you think amplified/mitigated the impacts?

Please try to use max 15 words

3.3 Is the response to drought and floods undermined by the current Covid-19 pandemic? *

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

3.3.1 Please write a few examples of how the response to drought/floods is undermined by the Covid-19 pandemic

Please try to use max 15 words

3.4 Have the government, NGOs and local communities undertaken different response actions given the combined impacts of the current events (e.g., drought, floods, locust infestation, Covid-19)? *

- Actions are integrated in order to respond effectively to the impacts of multiple shocks.
- Actions are not integrated and respond to the impacts of individual shocks.

3.4.1 Please write a few examples

3.5 What lessons learned from 2017-2018 were implemented in 2020? *

Please try to use max 15 words

3.6 Did you expect/predict the impact experienced in 2020? If not, what did you miss to consider? *

Please try to use max 15 words

3.7 Which information is your organization currently using to tackle compound risks? *

Compound risks: combination of natural events (e.g., heavy rains, hurricanes, etc.) and socio-economic events (e.g., political unrest, demographic change, etc.), occurring simultaneously and/or consecutively and leading to amplified or attenuated effects.

- Weather forecasts
- Food prices
- Crop yields
- Imports/Exports of goods
- GDP/GNI
- MUAC values
- Unemployment rates
- Violence & Conflicts
- Internal Displacement
- Refugee influxes
- Infant mortality rate
- Livelihood zones
- Other

b) What *other* information does your organization use? *

List other datasets/indicators that your organization uses and that are not mentioned in the above list.

3.8 What kind of information could help to timely predict the impacts of current compound events?

List information/datasets/indicators that your organization still do not have but you think could best support your work for tackling compound events

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